

Zero PM

Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances

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Online PFAS guide for companies

Work Package 4 – Market Transition

Deliverable Work Package Leader:
International Chemical Secretariat, ChemSec

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The present document has not yet received final approval from the European Commission and may be subject to changes.

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Project partners:

Summary

The European research project ZeroPM – “Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances” combines three interlinked strategies to tackle pollution with persistent and mobile (PM) substances:

Prevent, **Prioritize** and **Remove**.

Work package 4 called Market Transition will assist a market transition away from harmful PM substances. This deliverable is the result from task 4.2 "PFAS guide for downstream chemical using companies" which will build a user friendly PFAS guide for companies to identify PFAS in their products or manufacturing processes. The deliverable is the website itself for the PFAS guide and this report provides additional details in this regard.

On the 23rd of February 2023 ZeroPM partner and WP leader, ChemSec, published the online PFAS guide for companies on the ChemSec website: pfas.chemsec.org.

The guide was launched as a webinar to which 885 people signed up. At the peak there were 437 people listening live. There was a mixed audience with people from governments, NGOs and academia but the majority of attendees were from companies of different types. The slides and a recording of the webinar is available here:

<https://chemsec.org/webinar-we-know-if-you-have-pfas-in-your-products/>

To accompany the webinar, a press release was also sent out to relevant media:

https://chemsec.org/chemsec-helps-businesses-map-pfas-hotspots-ahead-of-eu-ban/?utm_source=twitter&utm_medium=social&utm_campaign=PFAS_Guide_230224

Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Context and background for the guide	6
3	About the Guide	7
4	Building the Guide	8

Appendices

Appendix: Press Release

1 Introduction

ZeroPM, which stands for Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances, is a 5 year long European research project funded under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. ZeroPM will interlink and synergize three strategies to protect the environment and human health from persistent and mobile (PM) substances: **Prevent**, **Prioritize** and **Remove**. To do this, ZeroPM will develop an evidence-based multilevel framework. The framework will guide policy, technological and market incentives to minimize use, emissions and pollution of entire groups of PM substances.

Work package 4: Market Transition has the main objective to catalyse a market transition away from harmful PM substances. This will be achieved by assisting, encouraging and connecting companies, who are at various stages of making this market transition, by producing tools that support industry to identify PM substances in their products and adopt PM substance alternatives and ensuring the perspective of companies producing and using PM substances and their alternatives is heard in the current and forthcoming policy changes.

This deliverable relates to task 4.2: PFAS guide for downstream chemical using companies and reports on the user friendly PFAS guide developed for companies to identify PFAS in their products or manufacturing processes. Information from existing and forthcoming publications and databases on PFAS uses, have been translated into a user-friendly interactive online tool. The deliverable itself is the website with the online guide for companies. This report provides additional information.

2 Context and background for the guide

Over the last years ChemSec has engaged in a dialogue with many companies about PFAS and the substitution of PFAS. This has been heightened by the PFAS movement <https://chemsec.org/pfas/> where companies who support legislative action, and that also have strategies in place to limit their own use of PFAS, together in a common forum. It has become obvious over time, that it is very difficult for many companies to know if they have PFAS in their processes and products.

There is a general awareness that has increased over the last years that for example, waterproof textiles and non-stick cookware are product groups that may contain PFAS, but other than these applications it is more often on an ad-hoc basis that companies happen to hear about other potential uses of PFAS, such as lubricants or coatings.

The identified resource gap needed to systematically map the possible uses of PFAS in businesses is a crucial first step towards a PFAS phaseout and was the main reason behind the decision to develop the PFAS guide.

The guide builds on existing inventories, reports and publications on PFAS uses from ZeroPM partners and other experts. These resources have been developed into a format

that is more easily accessible and understandable for non-scientists and people working more hands on with the PFAS issue in companies.

The PFAS guide is aimed at a user who is a person working for a company down the chemical supply chain, and who has been given the task to look into how the company could be affected by upcoming PFAS bans and increased requirements from customers.

The guide is easy enough for non-experts in chemistry or sustainability to use, but contains a wealth of information that should be beneficial for experienced sustainability experts.

3 About the Guide

The guide is a website which is free of charge to use, found at pfas.chemsec.org.

The guide contains one part with basic guidance and information in different areas related to PFAS (see screen shot to the left):

- The investigate section lists and explains typical PFAS uses showing red flags where these uses are suspected to contain PFAS.
- There is a section on supply chain communication explaining how and what to ask suppliers about PFAS.
- There is a section with a basic introduction to different methods for chemical analysis of PFAS in different types of products.
- The phaseout section gives a short introduction to substitution and alternatives assessment and links to further resources on this.
- There is a short summary of the regulatory situation for PFAS in the EU and the US.
- There are also links to good reports by others about PFAS and how to substitute PFAS in different sectors, such as Paints, Textiles, Food Packaging, Construction and more.

There is also a database where you can search for sectors, products, uses and functions to understand if you have "PFAS hotspots" in your business (see screen shot below).

There is also, when possible, links to the SIN List and the ChemSec Marketplace for alternatives as well as to other sources of information.

Possible PFAS hotspots
Based on your selection

698 results Download Excel Share link Remember search

Sector	Use/Product	Function	Material
Refrigerant systems	Mobile air conditioning	Refrigerants	-
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"><div>Possible alternatives ⓘ CO2 refrigerant Propane</div><div>PFAS CAS numbers ⓘ 115-25-3 356-18-3 377-41-3 76-16-4</div><div>Additional information Overview of F-gases and alternatives</div></div>			
> Textile, apparel and upholstery	(Sailing) boat equipment - textiles for maritime applications	Water and oil repellence	Textile
> Healthcare	Plastic anesthetic delivery systems	Component in material	-
> Energy Sector	Surface coatings for solar panels	Coating	-
	Reaction vessels, stirrers and other		

Knowledge about PFAS uses is a growing field and it is envisaged that the Guide will be a living and growing database. Users are very welcome to contact ChemSec with additional information on PFAS uses, or other information that could feed into the database. pfasguide@chemsec.org

4 Building the Guide

The work to build the guide started early on in 2022 with a number of workshops.

The first one was held online with selected scientific experts within ZeroPM. The aim of this workshop was to identify available publications and inventories from the academic sphere on PFAS uses, and to discuss which of these would be the best basis for building the PFAS guide.

For the second online workshop about ten companies that have worked actively to phase out PFAS were invited. The aim was to understand how these companies have gone about mapping PFAS in their business, what the main learnings and gaps they saw that the PFAS guide could fill.

The third workshop was in person with the two consultant firms that we contracted to work with the design and programming of the guide: <https://whereismypony.se>, <https://www.itiden.se>. The aim of this workshop was to present the idea behind the guide and the results from the two first workshops and from this to discuss how to design a user-friendly online guide to serve both sustainability experts but also less experienced professionals from different types of companies. The workshop was the start of a close collaboration with these consultants until the launch of the guide.

After this the work to build the database, write guiding texts and design the website started and it was worked on intensively over the whole of 2022 and January-February 2023. During this time, the guide has been discussed with individual companies and received additional input.

In December 2022 a beta version of the guide was opened for a number of companies that had volunteered to give input to the development of the guide. We received valuable feedback from H&M, COOP Denmark, Intersport, Kingfisher and Bestseller.

At the ZeroPM workshop in Gothenburg on the 7th and 8th of February 2023 (<https://zeropm.eu/events-prevention-workshop/>), a preview of the guide was given to the participants in the corresponding breakout session.

Appendix: Press Release

FEBRUARY 23, 2023

ChemSec helps businesses map PFAS hotspots ahead of EU ban

The EU's plans to ban PFAS will have a huge impact on companies globally. Perhaps even more than expected, as many manufacturers are unaware that they may have PFAS chemicals in their product line. ChemSec's new online tool — PFAS Guide — helps solve this problem.

Today, ChemSec launches the [PFAS Guide](#), which helps companies investigate the use of persistent chemicals within their businesses. The main feature of the PFAS Guide is the searchable database uncovering different PFAS uses and functions, but the online tool also provides guidance on different aspects of the phase-out process from regulation and investigation all the way to testing and supply chain communication.

"We've been working to support companies in chemical substitution for a long time, and the last few years we've gathered a group of companies working specifically on the PFAS issue. The discussions with them made it clear to us that a main challenge is understanding if and where in your business you may have PFAS", says Dr. Anna Lennquist, Project Leader for the PFAS Guide.

PFAS are a source of growing concern

A couple of weeks ago, a big [proposal to restrict PFAS](#) in the EU was published. The five EU Member States behind the proposal submitted a broad restriction proposal that clearly shows the need for the industry to put all resources into phasing out all PFAS substances.

"The PFAS Guide from ChemSec will be a valuable resource for any company"

At the same time, determination to get rid of “forever chemicals” is gaining momentum from other stakeholders as well. Over a [hundred companies](#) have, for example, come together to support a ban on PFAS.

“At Zound Industries, with our Brands Marshall and Urbanears, we are aware of the widespread use of PFAS in electronics. But we are on a mission to phase out PFAS in the headphones and speakers we design and sell, in order to make them circular. The PFAS Guide from ChemSec will be a valuable resource for any company in the industry”, says Anna Forsgren, Compliance and Sustainability Manager at Zound Industries.

Some of the world’s largest investment firms have also taken a stand. Last year, a group of investors sent out [a letter to chemical companies](#) encouraging them to stop the production of persistent chemicals. The success of the letter resulted in a recently launched formal [investors initiative](#) to tackle the PFAS crisis. The 50 institutional investors that are members of the initiative have more than US\$10 trillion of assets under management or advice.

“The step-by-step guide makes it easy to identify potential uses of PFAS in products”

With upcoming PFAS restrictions in the EU and elsewhere, the new online tool could not have come at a better time. How to phase out PFAS is something all companies — large and small — will need to analyse sooner rather than later.

“The PFAS Guide is a very useful tool. The step-by-step guide makes it easy to identify potential uses of PFAS in products and gives guidance on how to phase it out as well. It’s a great help for companies looking to ensure that their products are PFAS-free”, says Louisa Raith Sørensen, Strategic Project Leader at Coop.

About PFAS

PFAS have been manufactured and used in products such as make-up, non-stick pans, water- and greaseproof textiles, food-packaging materials,

and firefighting foam since the 1950s and are still used in a wide variety of products around the world today.

But they are also substances of growing concern due to their problematic properties. Per- and polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS) are a group of several thousand man-made chemicals that accumulate in the environment and [cause health impacts](#) for generations. They are, for example, linked to cancer, lung disease, diabetes, reproductive abnormalities and learning difficulties. Since PFAS do not degrade, these “forever chemicals” are now so widespread that it is safe to say that every single human being on the planet has detectable levels of these toxic chemicals in their blood.

[Go to PFAS Guide](#)

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The PFAS Guide has been developed by environmental NGO ChemSec as part of the EU-funded project ZeroPM. The project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101036756.

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[PFASPress Releases](#)

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